

DIRECTING SCHOOL STUDENTS TO SPORT TYPES TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THEIR PHYSICAL FITNESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7485573>

Abstract: The role of physical education classes in the healthy and well-rounded formation of schoolchildren is incomparable, because physical education is the only educational subject that forms a conscious attitude to oneself and one's body, the need to strengthen health, and educates voluntary and moral qualities. The use of a variety of tools and methods by the physical education teacher in teaching athletics exercises in physical education classes and teaching most of the exercises that are difficult to perform in accepting the standards of athletics will prevent the lesson process from becoming boring. Therefore, one of the effective methods of organizing a physical education lesson is the methods of games and competitions.

Keywords: physical training, quality development, physical education, comprehensive school, game and competition methods.

Relevance: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 5, 2021 "On measures to further increase the quality of the formation of the reserve of athletes in Olympic and Paralympic sport by fundamentally improving the system of sport training", November 5, 2021 "XXXIII Summer Olympics to be held in Paris (France) in 2024" and determination of the tasks to be carried out in the resolutions PQ-5281 "On comprehensive training of our athletes for the XVII Paralympic Games" puts great tasks before the specialists of the field. At the same time, the secondary school plays an important role in the education system as the main link. The development of physical training, sports and wellness activities in educational institutions, increasing the interest of students in sports, and strengthening their knowledge, skills, and abilities is becoming a demand of the time. In view of the full implementation of these issues, "State Education Standards" on physical education were developed and put into practice. This standard defines the basic requirements for the knowledge, skills and abilities and educational load that athletes in the general education system should acquire.

As a result of the scientific examination of the functional readiness of school-aged children, it has been confirmed that physical exercises play a decisive role in the development of the body.

The results of experiments conducted by many scientists show that the dynamics of physical formation and physical training of a person depends on the student's ability to work and the nature and volume of regular physical exercises.

In their research, many scientists have shown that the study of how the functional capacity of the children's body is affected by the load given to the muscles is an important issue at present.

Issues of development of physical fitness of students, moderation of physical exercise load are sufficiently covered. However, due to the fact that sports are getting younger and the

consciousness of young students is growing at a high level in the current progressive period, it is the need of the hour to introduce additional new loads to the science of physical education. Currently, a lot of information has been collected on how excessive physical load affects the body of athletes, but there are many cases of giving them the same physical load without taking into account the characteristics of the body of young students.

Determining the laws of development of all qualities depending on age is of great importance, because the motor analyzer develops from childhood and the foundation of future sports results is laid during this period. A number of researchers determined that it is appropriate to start developing qualities from childhood and adolescence. In particular, on the selection of athletes for sports, involvement in training, planning and management of training, F.A. Kerimov,

Scientific studies were carried out by O. V. Goncharova, V. N. Nikitushkin, M. N. Umarov, K. T. Shakirjonova, N. T. Tokhtaboev, M. S. Olimov and other scientists {4.5}.

The role of physical education classes in the formation of healthy and well-rounded schoolchildren is incomparable, because physical education is the only educational subject that forms a conscious attitude to oneself and one's body, the need to strengthen health, and educates voluntary and moral qualities. The use of a variety of tools and methods by the physical education teacher in teaching athletics exercises in physical education classes and teaching most of the exercises that are difficult to perform in accepting the standards of athletics will prevent the lesson process from becoming boring. Therefore, one of the effective methods of organizing a physical education lesson is the methods of games and competitions. These game and competition methods are versatile and are used in a wide range of ways to increase students' motor activity.

However, the fact that the physical education classes held in general education schools are not formed at the level of demand will not fail to have an impact on the training system of reserve athletes.

It limits the possibilities of finding talented students and directing them to sports in the physical education classes of general education schools. Involvement in physical education and sports in general education schools is considered one of the urgent tasks of state importance today.

The object of the study: Methodology of teaching movement games and athletics in physical education classes conducted with 4th grade students of a general education school.

Research results and its discussion: When teaching athletics in physical education classes in general education schools, it is necessary to organize them through games and competition methods, because the methods of games and competitions are a way of figuratively organizing the lesson process, in which the child matures spiritually, physically and mentally, and develops and is educated in all aspects. For this reason, we conducted a study by using specially selected game and competition methods in physical education classes of general education school students. In this case, 4 "A" grade students in the control group were taught and observed physical education program lessons in the traditional way. In the physical education lessons of 4 "B" grade students in the experimental group, lessons were organized based on the program developed within the framework of the research, and game and competition methods were used in the teaching of athletics.

The purpose of the study: Improving the effectiveness of teaching athletics techniques to 4th-grade students in physical education classes of a comprehensive school by using competitions and games incorporating athletics exercises.

Tasks of research: Determining physical fitness of secondary school students.

- To study the structure and content of athletics classes in the physical education program of secondary school students.

-Using competitions and games incorporating athletics exercises in physical education classes.

- Development of effective methods of teaching athletics techniques in general school classes.

Methodology of using action games for physical fitness and development of general education school students

Table 1

The order of operation	Orientation of action games	The types of games.
Action games of individual order	Emotional compatibility.	"Change of place", "Leader", "Urban" "The Fox and the Hare"
Action games in pairs	Feeling your partner in the team, anticipating their actions ability to see, to develop effective joint task solving.	"Reiner", "Swan and Ducks", "Sly fox", "We are happy our children", "Trap"
Team action games	Development of effective work together in small groups (team).	"Runs", "Leader", "Relay in a circle", "Who is fast", "Get into the ring"

Physical education classes in secondary schools twice a week

45 minutes passed. A control group (13 boys) and an experimental group (13 boys) were selected.

The study was carried out in the following order: individual action games, pair action games, team action games.

GET INTO THE CIRCLE

Children stand in a circle. A large belt is placed in the middle or a circle is drawn (a circle made of rope or drawn on the floor is 1-1.5 m in diameter). Children standing in a circle at a distance of 2-3 steps from the circle (In the game there are bags filled with sand. With the teacher's signal "Throw it!", all the children throw the bags into the circle. Then the teacher says "Pick up the bags". Children take the bags and come to their places. The game is repeated 4-6 times.

Game rule: The bags must be held flat. {2.3}

At the beginning and at the end of the study, in order to determine the physical qualities and physical fitness of the students of the experimental and control groups, 30 m pre-start run, 30 m high start run, standing long jump, standing triple jump, 1000 m run, throwing the ball forward tests were taken and performance techniques were evaluated (tables 2-3).

Dynamics of indicators of the level of physical fitness of the subjects of the control group before and after the study

Table 2

№	FULL NAME	Year of birth	30-m pre-start run (seconds)		30m high jump (seconds)		1000 m run (second)		Standing long jump (cm)		Triple jump from standing position (cm)		Throwing the filler ball forward (cm)	
			T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K
1	M-ov. A	2011	5,4	5,3	6,3	5,3	5,32	6,2	1,44	1,46	4,02	4,15	5,25	5,53
2	X-hunt. R	2010	5,4	5,3	6,3	5,3	5,25	6,1	1,28	1,29	4,16	4,21	5,74	5,75
3	D-ou. M	2010	5,6	5,5	6,1	5,5	5,22	5,8	1,42	1,27	4,20	4,32	5,42	5,46
4	Z-ov. A	2010	5,7	5,5	6,1	5,5	6,08	5,9	1,28	1,34	4,26	4,34	6,10	6,04
5	J-ov. S	2011	5,8	5,7	6,2	5,7	5,11	6,0	1,35	1,42	4,35	4,42	5,84	5,74
6	X-hun. I	2010	5,2	5,5	5,6	5,5	5,28	5,6	1,37	1,41	4,13	4,23	6,02	6,10
7	D-ov. M	2010	5,5	5,4	5,7	5,4	5,34	5,7	1,33	1,37	4,05	4,24	5,91	5,98
8	M-ov. L	2011	5,8	5,7	6,1	5,7	6,10	6,0	1,32	1,38	4,20	4,25	5,32	5,36
9	K-ov. I	2011	5,7	5,6	6,0	5,6	5,52	5,8	1,37	1,39	4,17	4,25	5,47	5,54
10	B-ou. S	2010	5,8	5,5	5,9	5,5	5,38	5,7	1,26	1,36	4,30	4,36	6,01	5,45
11	A-ov. D	2010	5,8	5,8	6,0	5,8	5,61	5,9	1,36	1,39	4,21	4,29	5,14	5,16
12	T-hun. J	2011	5,9	5,4	6,1	5,4	5,12	6,0	1,54	1,56	4,26	4,26	5,26	5,32
13	S-ov. F	2010	5,7	5,6	5,9	5,6	5,78	5,6	1,45	1,52	4,10	4,19	5,62	5,35
$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$			5,6±0,2	5,5±0,1	6,02±0,2	5,5±0,1	5,47±0,3	5,39±0,2	1,36±0,1	1,39±0,1	4,18±0,1	4,27±0,1	5,62±0,3	5,59±0,3

Note: The control group's 30-m start sprint improved by 5.6±0.2 before the study and by 5.5±0.1 after the study. 30-m high start running improved by 6.02±0.2 before the study and by 5.5±0.1 after the study. 1000m running improved to 5.47±0.3 before the study and 5.39±0.2 after the study. Standing long jump improved to 1.36±0.1 before the study and 1.39±0.1 after the study. Standing triple jump improved to 4.23±0.1 before the study and 4.47±0.1 after the study. The filler ball forward throw improved to 5.52 ±0.3 before the study and 5.59 ± 0.2 after the study.

**Dynamics of indicators of the level of physical fitness of experimental group subjects
before and after the study**

Table 3

№	FULL NAME	Year of birth	30-m pre-start run (seconds)		30m high jump (seconds)		1000 m run (second)		Standing long jump (cm)		Triple jump from standing position (cm)		Throwing the filler ball forward (cm)	
			T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K	T\A	T\K
1	B-oti R	2011	5,2	5,2	6,1	5,6	5,12	5,11	1,47	1,49	4,14	4,21	5,3 5	5,39
2	M-ov. X	2010	5,3	5,1	6,0	5,7	5,15	5,23	1,29	1,35	4,13	4,35	5,8 0	5,54
3	M-ov. S	2011	5,7	5,4	6,1	5,6	5,12	5,14	1,45	1,43	4,27	4,62	5,5 2	5,65
4	M-ov. M	2012	5,6	4,9	5,9	5,2	6,1	5,42	1,37	1,32	4,28	4,60	6,1 2	5,90
5	M-ov. M	2011	5,7	5,2	6,0	5,6	5,20	5,10	1,45	1,51	4,38	4,52	5,8 9	5,88
6	Q-ur. A	2011	5,3	5,1	5,6	5,4	5,22	5,11	1,39	1,35	4,17	4,35	6,1 1	5,24
7	R-ov. A	2010	5,4	5,4	5,7	5,8	5,39	5,21	1,38	1,51	4,09	4,34	5,9 8	5,51
8	G'-ov. M	2010	5,7	5,2	6,1	5,5	5,57	5,35	1,39	1,57	4,28	4,61	5,4 8	5,64
9	Hon. B	2010	5,6	5,1	6,0	5,4	5,56	5,34	1,38	1,64	4,19	4,64	5,5 2	5,54
10	A-ov. S	2011	5,7	5,1	5,9	5,4	5,34	5,22	1,37	1,68	4,35	4,35	6,0 9	6,42
11	X-hunt. B	2011	5,8	5,3	6,0	5,5	5,55	5,29	1,36	1,58	4,29	4,45	5,4 7	5,42
12	T-hun. K	2010	5,8	5,2	6,1	5,6	5,12	4,53	1,54	1,69	4,35	4,56	5,2 8	5,52
13	M-avlo. F	2010	5,6	5,2	5,8	5,5	5,68	5,04	1,45	1,45	4,19	4,62	5,7 8	5,69
$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$			5,5± 0,2	5,2± 0,1	5,9± 0,1	5,5± 0,1	5,39± 0,2	5,10± 0,1	1,40± 0,05	1,51± 0,1	4,23± 0,1	4,47± 0,1	5,7 2 ±0,3	6,64± 0,2

Note: The experimental group improved 5.5 ± 0.2 in 30-m start running before the study and 5.2 ± 0.1 after the study. 30-m high start running improved by 6.02 ± 0.2 before the study and by 5.5 ± 0.1 after the study. 1000m running improved from 5.47 ± 0.3 before the study to 5.10 ± 0.1 after the study. Standing long jump improved to 1.40 ± 0.05 before the study and 1.51 ± 0.1 after the study. Standing triple jump improved to 4.23 ± 0.1 before the study and 4.47 ± 0.1 after the study. The filler ball forward throw improved from 5.72 ± 0.3 before the study to 6.64 ± 0.2 after the study.

A general diagram of the formation of the level of physical fitness of the subjects of the experimental group and the control group at the end of the study

When the difference between the two groups was compared in the table of the growth dynamics of the indicators during the experiment, it was found that all the indicators in the experimental group were much higher than the indicators in the control group. For example: the increase in the 30-m pre-start run in the control group is equal to 0.1 seconds, while in the experimental group these indicators are equal to 0.3 seconds; In the 30-m high-start running test, the increase in the control group is equal to 0.3 seconds, while in the experimental group, these indicators are equal to 0.4 seconds. In the 1000 m run, the increase in the control group is equal to 0.6 seconds, while in the experimental group these indicators are equal to 0.38 seconds; standing long jump in the control group, the increase is 3 cm, in the experimental group, these indicators are 47 cm; in the control group, the increase in standing long jump test was equal to 9 cm, in the experimental group, these indicators increased by 24 cm; in the control group, the increase in the ball forward test was equal to 7 cm, in the experimental group, these indicators increased by 92 cm.

SUMMARY.

Physical education classes in general education schools should be organized through the methods of games and competitions in teaching athletics, because the methods of games and competitions are a way of figuratively organizing the lesson process, in which the child matures spiritually, physically and mentally, and develops and is educated in all aspects. For this reason, we conducted the research by using the game and competition methods selected from the study of physical education classes of secondary school students. The analysis of the literature showed that national and action games, relays (fun starts) and interesting competitions in secondary schools take the main place and have a positive effect on the

formation of mental and movement skills and competencies, as well as education of all qualities, abilities and qualities of students.

The use of athletics and the game method in the course of physical education training helps elementary school students to achieve higher levels of physical development and training, and to make training more interesting.

Based on this planning, the following results were recorded by using the athletics and game method in the physical education classes in the general education school: the experimental group's 30m pre-start run increased by 5.4%. 30-m high start running increased by 6.7%. 1000 m run increased by 5.7%. Standing long jump increased by 7.2%. Standing triple jump increased by 7.3%. 7.4% increase in fill ball forward. It can be seen that the applied program gave its results and this program justified itself.

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